

Visual representations and learning obstacles for definite integrals in first semesters undergraduate students, a preliminary report

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Abstract

This study is the first on a sequel, and a preliminary diagnostic study in the area of Didactics of Mathematics, which aims to review the teaching strategies for the Integral Calculus course, before carrying out the subsequent pedagogical field interventions. We targeted the most difficult topics for the students and described some of the variables which are potentially engaged in the performance of students and the survival and desertion rates in the first semesters of technical careers. In sections 1 and 2 the reader will find general information, the methodology and protocol applied in this research. Sections 3, 4 and 5 are dedicated to evaluating the subjective perception of difficulty reported by students, and using this variable to determine the topics that merit direct didactic intervention in the classroom. Section 6 explains the treatment given to the control group and the experimental group, in relation to the evaluation of visual thinking and the didactic intervention applied. Sections 7 and 8 are dedicated to the discussion of the final results and conclusions.

Keywords: Active Learning; Riemann integral, visual representations.

1 Introduction

Students of Integral Calculus (IC) courses, use to present different cognitive resistances which can hinder their understanding of the notion of Riemann integrals (Tharayil, 2018). These difficulties could be related to the different visualization capacities of the students (Huang, 2015) as well as the semiotic nature (Winsløw, 2004). Our general problem is to find effective teaching strategies to address this issue, this study is a preliminary diagnostic survey on the general teaching-learning situation prior to the subsequent pedagogical interventions. We describe some of the variables which are potentially engaged in the performance of students and the survival and desertion rates, in order to provide some guidelines on the nature of the didactical work that should be done. These goals are aligned with the objectives 1, 2 and especially 4 of the UN agenda on sustainable development (ONU, 2022), so as for the local policy of the Colombian government (SPADIES, 2015) and the internal UNAL policy (Pinto, 2007).

2 Experimental Design

2.1 Methodology

The protocol we chose is the design of a descriptive-analytic statistical survey, in the form of a non-simultaneous double-blind study, applied in two phases. In the first phase we constituted a sample of repeating IC students, which was refined using demographic criteria. A questionnaire was administered to the subjects in order to assess their subjective perception of the difficulty of IC topics, which was used to determine the topics that required a didactic intervention. In the second phase, a control group of repeat students was drawn from the initial sample. A sequence of didactic situations aimed at addressing the determined didactic topics

was applied. In the next semester, this same sequence was applied to a new sample made up of students who were taking CI for the first time.

2.2 First phase sampling frame and inclusion-exclusion criteria

Through a public invitation, we contacted students who enrolled for the two upper Calculus subjects (Integral and Multivariate) in the semester 2023-2 at the UNAL. We wanted the subjects to explain their experiences with previous IC courses. We accepted all students who had completely attended the IC at least once. We excluded first time students as well as those who had dropped out.

2.3 Constitution of the sample

The initial group was constituted by 85 subjects who attended classes with 4 different classrooms and were chosen by simple random samplings. We applied a simple statistical study with the purpose of detecting concomitant variables. The minimum age of the subjects was 17 years, the maximum age was 47 years. The average age of the sample was 21.94 years, with a standard deviation of 5.192378 years. We asked for the biological sex of our subjects, 66 of 85 which (77.64 %) were men, 18 (21.17 %) were women, and 1 subject preferred not to declare. We asked about the name and type of institution, the faculty and the undergraduate program they had previously attended. 3 subjects in the sample (3.53 %) had previously studied in private institutions, the rest (82 in total, 96.47 %) had studied at public universities. 1 individual in the group (1.17 %) came from having previously studied in a statistics program, 8 subjects (9.41 %) came from careers in natural sciences, 4 (4.7 %) from programs in Economics, Agronomy or Social Sciences, and 2 (2.35 %) came from other programs such as Veterinary Medicine. The rest (70 individuals, 82.36 %) had studied some undergraduate engineering program. 81 individuals did not finish the program they had previously enrolled, but rather had withdrawn from the first institution in order to start again at the UNAL. Asked about the year in which they had last enrolled in the IC subject, one individual decided not to answer, it turned out to be a 22-year-old student from UNAL, we withdrew him from the sample. The rest of the subjects' answers (83 individuals, 97.65 %) were between 2000 and the first semester of 2003, with mean $\bar{x} = 2022$ and standard deviation $s = 1.238497$. The sample was finally made up of 82 students, coming from different university institutions, public and private, with age ranges between 17 and 29 years, and had enrolled for the last time after 2017. From now, we will call this group the **triage group (TG)** of this study.

3 Students' Perception of Difficulty

We applied a short questionnaire to TG subjects in order to compare the student's perception of difficulty.

- Question 1. "Please tell us how difficult each of the following topics was at the time you studied them for the first time, just as you remember and according to your perception. Use a scale from 0 to 5 where 0 represents a topic which was so easy that it did not present any difficulty for you, 3 is a topic or skill of intermediate difficulty and 5 was an issue that you considered very difficult or impossible to understand at that time".

We made a list of about 25 topics in the IC program. The measurements varied very little between the topics belonging to the same thematic, so we chose a single representing topic for those presenting similar behaviors, these are the ones which remained clearly distinguishable. **L:** Limit definition with ϵ - δ formula. **LUB:** Least upper bound (LUB). **Series** (definition, examples and criteria). **RS:** Riemann sums. **RI:** Riemann integral definition. **TFC:** The fundamental theorems of Calculus. **VC:** Change of variables (solution of indefinite integrals by). **IbP:** Integration by parts. **TS:** Trigonometric substitutions. **W:** Weierstrass 'substitutions.

They were classified according to the subjective perception of their intrinsic difficulty, as: **Easy**: Those whose median is $M = 2$ and 3rd quartile $q_3 \leq 3$. Among those we have the notion of Riemann Sums, the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus and the technique of changing variables for solving an indefinite integral. **Intermediate type A**: Those for which $M = q_3 = 3$. The only item satisfying this is the topic of limits with the ε - δ definition. **Intermediate type B**: Those whose median is $M = 2$ and 3rd quartile $q_3 = 4$. Among those we have the definition of Riemann integrals and the method of integration by parts. **Intermediate to difficult**: Those with $M = 3$ and $q_3 = 4$. Among those we have the definition of Least Upper Bound, the notion of Series and its examples, and the resolution of indefinite integrals by trigonometric Change of variables. **Difficult**: Those with $M = 3 = q_1$. The only item satisfying this is the topic of resolution of indefinite integrals with the Weierstrass 'substitution.

Figure 1. Box plots for answers of question 1, the topics described considered as different variables.

The difference between the intermediate classes A and B is not in the median, but in the dispersion of the data. For class A, 50 % of the data (quartiles 2 and 3) is concentrated between 2 and 3, so the perception of the students is that the topic presents an intermediate difficulty, neither very high nor very low. On the other hand, for class B the scores have been dispersed between 1 and 4, leaving the median at 2 and the mean a little above, between 2 and 3. So there is a general perception that the topic is intermediate, but there is also a larger number of subjects who think it is easy or difficult.

- Question 2, "Among the listed topics, in your own perception, which is the most difficult?" The choices were the same as in question 1. 2 subjects (2.44 %) answered L, 2 (2.44 %) LUB, 21 (25.61 %) S, 4 (4.88 %) RS, 7 (8.54 %) RI, 1 (1.22 %) TFC, 3 (3.67 %) VC, 2 (2.44 %) IbP, 13 (15.85 %) TS, and 4 (4.88 %) W.
- Question 3, "Is there any topic not mentioned in the above list that, according to your appreciation, was very difficult? Which one?" 58 of the subjects (70.73 %) answered No. The rest of the subjects mentioned many different additional topics, which were grouped in the following representative labels, **SR**: Solids in revolution. **PF**: Partial fractions. **T**: Trigonometry (identities, angles and applications). **TP**: Trigonometric powers (indefinite integrals of). **PC**: Polar coordinates. **PS**: Power series (Convergence criteria, Taylor theorem, etc.). **App**: Applications of definite integrals. 10 subjects (12.20 %) answered SR, 2 (2.44 %) PF, 2 (2.44 %) T, 2 (2.44 %) TP, 5 (6.1 %) PC, 2 (2.44 %) PS, and 2 (2.44 %) App.

4 Determination of Pertinent Topics

Assigning to each variable the sum of the correlations with respect to the other different variables in the list, we obtain function of cumulative correlations with respect to the topics 'difficulty as perceived by students. We decided to consider this function as a measurement of the pertinence of the topics. A particular topic X was considered pertinent if its cumulative correlation $f(X)$ satisfied $f(X) \geq 4$. Five topics entered this criterion: RS, RI, TFC, VC and IbP, for which respectively $f(RS) = 4.359788$, $f(RI) = 4.384189$, $f(TFC) = 5.122916$, $f(VC) = 4.898077$, and $f(IbP) = 4.823379$. Notice that the answers to questions 2 and 3 contradicted this criterion. It should now be pointed out that this survey was about the subjective perception of students. Due

to the answers to questions 2 and 3, we included the topics of series (S), trigonometric substitutions (TS) and solids in revolution (SR). The list of relevant issues in the IC course, according to the student's perception of difficulty, was made up of 8 topics, namely S, RS, RI, TFC, TS, VC, IbP and SR. These are the topics we chose to target in a first intervention.

5 Didactical Approach on The First Encounter

We explored the information which was available to the students, with respect to the didactical approach used in their first approach of IC.

- Question 4, "*Which of these teaching tools or classroom strategies were used by your first teacher of IC?*". Student had to answer Yes or No to each item of the following, **CbH**: Calculations by hand. **P**: Plots by hand or any other means, included computer graphics such as Geogebra or Desmos. **L**: Logical proofs (such as ϵ - δ limit proofs by definition, or proofs by induction in \mathbb{N}). **SV**: Semiotic-Visual diagrams, such as flowcharts, mind maps or graphical calculators. See (Alson, 1987), (Castillo et al, 2023). **NPL**: Numeric Programs or Computational Languages such as MatLab, Python, etc. 69 subjects (84.15 %) answered Yes for CbH, 59 (71.95 %) for P, 51 (62 %) for L, 22 (26.84 %) for SV and 21 (25.61 %) for NPL. The prevalent strategies for teaching IC continue to be CbH, P and L, the most used in a traditional master classes. The use of other methods was remarkably lower.
- Question 5, "*In the most difficult topic, what was the tool/strategy used by the teacher?*". The possible choices were, as in question 4, CbH for calculus by hand, P for plots, L for logic and proofs, SV for semiotic-visual, NPL for numeric or computational algorithms. 27 subjects (32.93 %) answered CbH, 3 (3.67 %) L, 1 (1.21 %) L, and 2 (2.44 %) NPL.
- Question 6, "*What was the predominant didactic approach used by the teacher with which you first saw these notions?*". The choices were **NA** No Answer, **NAP** The teacher did not have a clear didactical approach, **Pol** Polya's resolution of problems, **FC** Flipped classroom, **ST** STEAM education, **DS** Didactical situations, and **O** Other. 30 subjects (36.59 %) answered NA, 28 (34.15 %) NAP, 11 (13.41 %) Pol, 4 (4.88 %) FC, 4 (4.88 %) ST, 3 (3.67 %) DS, 2 (2.44 %) O.
- Question 7 we asked, "*On the most difficult topic, would you have preferred that the teacher used a different tool/approach?*" 33 subjects (40.24 %) answered Yes, the rest of the sample (59.76 %) answered No.

We invited the subjects of the initial sample to continue in our study. 52 subjects answered affirmatively and conformed the sample for the 2nd questionnaire. From those, three students withdrew due to different reasons. The TG was reduced to the remaining 49 volunteers.

6 Visual Thinking Assessment

Many sources persuaded us that our didactical intervention should involve changes in our teaching strategies (Attorps et al, 2013), (González, 2022), through the design of didactic situations (Brousseau, 2002) focused on visual thinking with logical and numerical processes (Pritchard, 2022). Others like (Godino et al, 2021), (Winsløw, 2004), have dealt with the need to identify the types of images that students use in their visualization processes. In order to measure the students' visualization skills, we applied the instrument presented in (Huang, 2015). The original survey was administered to 15 students, chosen among the top 10 % of their pairs, which allowed the author to interview each subject individually. The place where the survey was carried on is Taiwan, whose demographic differences with respect to Colombia are evident. The results of this work can be considered, in some extent, as a standardization of Huang's test.

The visual thinking skills were categorized to 5 competencies and three levels. **NV**: Non-visual level, the students focus on a single visual image, prefer to solve problems using symbolic representations, and rely on analytical thinking instead. **LV**: Local-visual, the students can perceive relationships among various visual images, however there is a lack of coherence in the representative system. **GV**: Global-visual, the students can use the relationships to construct a consistent structure based on the relationships among various visual

images. This consistency determines the scope of visual thinking. Following (Huang, 2015), the test for measuring the visual thinking was constituted by the following tasks,

- (1) Given that $\int_1^3 f(t)dt = 8.6$, use two different strategies in order to evaluate $\int_2^4 f(t)dt$.
- (2) The graph of a function f is sketched in figure 4. Given that $\int_{-2}^5 f(t)dt = \frac{39}{8}$, determine the value of the constant C .
- (3) Is it true or false that, if $\int_a^b f(x)dx \geq \int_a^b g(x)dx$, then $f(x) \geq g(x)$ for all $a \leq x \leq b$? Please justify your answer.
- (4) If $\int_1^5 f(x)dx = 10$, use two different strategies in order to evaluate $\int_1^5 (f(x) + 2)dx = 10$.
- (5) Use two different strategies in order to calculate $\int_{-3}^3 |x - 2|dx$.

Figure 2. Curve related to question

6.1 Application of the survey

This study was initially applied to the reduced TG, without any previous didactical intervention. For the semester 2024I we reapplied it on two new samples: (a) A group of 33 students who were subjected to some of our didactical situations and teaching strategies, with semiotic/visual tools, before applying the study, which will be called the Experimental Group (EG). (b) A group of 20 students who followed a traditional master class course, which will be called the Control Group (CG). The study was applied to both groups as one more within the rest of the evaluations carried out, without warning them about its purpose. The responses were reviewed, focusing solely on this aspect.

For the application of the survey, we followed some criteria that varied a little from the original study. In order to perform simple statistical analysis, we assigned a numerical score to each level of visual thinking, 0 for NV, 0.5 for LV, 1 for GL. In the original study, the author interviewed each student separately. Given the size of our samples, we decided to only take written responses. We encouraged students to explain, as much as they could and in their own words, the thought process they were carrying out. We applied a correction factor to the written scores as follows: Any response alone, without a justification, was scored as 0 (NV). Any response whose wording was confusing was scored as 0 (NV). Any response in which there was no evidence of visual thinking was scored as 0 (NV). Any response in which there was evidence of visual thinking, but the representations (i) were not coherent with each other, or (ii) were not integrated into the symbolic-algebraic response; were scored 0.5 (LV). Any response in which there was evidence of several mutually coherent representations, or that were integrated into symbolic-algebraic reasoning, were scored 1 (GV).

6.2 Didactical intervention on the experimental group

For our didactical intervention on the EG we followed the didactical situations of (Brousseau, 2002), using the graphical calculators (Alson, 1987), these are diagrams similar to the flowcharts in computing sciences, they allow students to recognize the underlying presence of an algorithm,

Figure 3. Alson's diagrams, called "graphical calculators".

They can also be used in order to explain the 2nd Fundamental Theorem of Calculus and illustrate antiderivatives, similar semiotic relations underlie among functions, derivatives and integrals. Our main idea was to grasp the notion of Riemann integral by organizing these sets of situations;

- Preliminary situations: arithmetic operations, the notion of area, basic instructions in R.
- Geometric/numeric situations: We treated Riemann sums from basic shapes to positive real continuous functions. The purpose is to approximate areas without knowing how to find antiderivatives. As an example, we treated the problem of measuring the area of a unit-circle. The situation develops around the approximation of the area of the circle, first with known figures (inscribed or circumscribed squares), later with rectangular subdivisions (Riemann partitions, without formalities). Using the insights and the knowledge acquired in the former basic situations, the first steps can be done with a pocket calculator. As more intermediate points are added, the approximations get narrower until, at some point, the process becomes ridiculously tedious. The teacher stops the game and asks: "How can we do this faster?", or "Can we do this better with a computer?". So we pass from calculating areas to the design of a numerical algorithm which will approximate the number π . A debate will arise about the heights of the intermediate points, the function $f(x) = \sqrt{1-x^2}$ and its role. It is possible to talk also about approximation errors. There will appear the need of an agreement about what a "reasonable" approximation is.
- Symbolic/algorithmic situations: We dealt with basic antiderivatives which can be usually solved either by substitution, or by a simple change of variables. The student needs to recognize "someone's derivative" and apply the Fundamental Theorem of Calculus. This can also be used to construct a primitive function $F(x)$ placed at a particular point of the real line $a \in \mathbb{R}$, and whose value $F(x)$ on each $a \leq x \leq b$ is the definite integral of $f(x)$ on the subinterval $[a, x]$, which can be now calculated with similar R-codes. The numerical method does not depend on the student's ability to calculate antiderivatives. The "reasonable approximation" criterion agreed before will now be applied. Then the Riemann sum provides the equivalent of a key in a pocket calculator, and can therefore be represented with Alson's diagrams. Although the semiotic relations of its components remain, the objects in the ovals are neither numbers/constants nor letters/variables, but functions/processes. We will refer to them as 2nd level diagrams.

```

% R-code template for Riemann sums
% with a 'reasonable' approximation <10^(-6)
a=ZZZ % fill in the ZZZ with the value of extreme a
b=ZZZ % fill in the ZZZ with the value of extreme b
n= 10^6*roof((b-a))
F=function(X)(ZZZ) % fill in the ZZZ with the
% instructions for the integrand function f(x)
x=seq(a, b, by=1/n)
Int=sum(F(x))/n
Int
    
```


Figure 4. Construction of a 2nd level(Alson's diagram with a R-code template.

- Inter-validating situations: The Social validation of the knowings within the classroom was achieved by a series of mutual interactions between students, through the comparison of outcomes in the competitive and collaborative games proposed by each didactic situation. For more details, see (Castillo et al, 2021).

7 Results

We have remarked before the qualitative results that one can obtain by applying this sort of visual/semiotic didactical situations. **Teacher-student relationships:** The interaction with students is therefore a reconfiguration factor in the approach to obstacles and resistances, so teacher-student relationships improve when compared to the master classes. **Comprehension of the problem:** Through a progressive didactical phase design, students in the experimental groups gain a deeper understanding of the subtle aspects of the integral. **Interactions within the classroom:** Since the truth is not based on authority, but rather in experimentation, knowledge is built as a social construction. Now we are also able to measure the effect that

the application of this type of didactic situations in a field intervention has on students' visual thinking and its integration into symbolic logical thinking.

Figure 5. Visual thinking results for the three groups. Left: (TG) Triage group of repeating students. Center: (EG) Experimental group subjected to visual/semiotic didactic situations before the test. Right: (CG) Control group exposed to a traditional master class without any other didactical methodology or teaching strategy.

In figure 5 the behavior of the variables that correspond to the tasks of the Visual Thinking Test is shown separately, for each of the samples. The following common features and global differences between the three samples can be seen. Except for task 1, the group that develops greater use of visual thinking abilities in the rest of the tasks is the experimental group, in which a simple intervention was applied, made up of a battery of didactic situations that we will explain in detail in another article to appear, which were developed before the application of the study. This is followed by the triage group, which generally showed a lower use of visual thinking skills. The group with the lowest level of visual thinking is the control group. In neither of the last two groups were teaching situations used before applying the study. Our interpretation of these results is that, possibly, the students in the triage group developed some of the visualization skills on their own during the semesters in which they had to repeat the course.

Figure 6. Visual thinking results for total score variable.

An additional variable was calculated with the sum of all visual thinking scores on each task. This total score whose value ranged between 0 and 5 points, constitutes a kind of global appreciation of the students' visual thinking. The fact that the experimental group showed a greater use of visual thinking at the global and local levels, shows to some extent the result of the didactic intervention carried out in the experimental group. The improvement in tasks 3 and 5 indicates better integration and coherence between visual representations and logical-symbolic solutions. When observing the total score variable of the levels of visual thinking, a fairly similar behavior is observed. The experimental group has a higher mean than the other two, and the dispersion of the scores is more upward, with a greater width of the range.

8 Final Conclusions

This work is an attempt to justify the relevance of a didactic intervention with visual-semiotic tools, aimed at processes that involve visual thinking. Our results point to the need of a greater teaching effort on visual representations and their logical, symbolic and semiotic relationships with the rest of the mathematics involved. When observing the final results, the scores on task 2 (the simplest in our first opinion) were striking for us. It barely involved the calculation of basic areas and the relationship between the algebraic sign and the graphical position (height) of a point in the Real plane. Paradoxically, this was the task that yielded the worst performance in the three groups. Two explanations for this are: (a) Since it was a question that required basic high school skills, it was not addressed by us through any didactic situation. The low scores reflect that, even in the first semesters of university, Colombian students overlook these basic relationships. In response, we should design a series of didactic situations especially aimed at this issue. (b) Low scores in task 2 may also be due to the cognitive dissonance caused by the didactic contract (Brousseau, 2002). Students expecting tricky questions about functions and integrals, were surprised by a problem that asked for basic areas and algebraic signs (D'Amore, 2006).

Finally, we wanted to show a comparison of the final grades of the control and experimental groups. The current student's strike at the UNAL dramatically changed the 2024I academic calendar, preventing us from accomplishing this task. However, we hope to fill this gap soon.

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